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Cloud-Operated Open Literate Educational Resources: the case of the MyBinder

Alberto Corbi, Daniel Burgos and Antonio María Pérez

Abstract—Literate programming and cloud-operated open literate educational resources (COOLER) have been catching the attention of the education community in recent years. This set of learning materials mainly comprises digital notebook-like documents which are stored, backed, and delivered from cloud services and eventually displayed in students' web browsers. As we demonstrate in this work, the advent of cloud architectures and the COVID-19 pandemic (which forced worldwide long-term distant academic environments) fortuitously teamed up with this learning and methodological trend by easing its use and fostering its adoption. With more detail, we have quantitatively measured the impact that the COOLER paradigm has had on the teaching realm by analyzing 5 years of logged data gathered by its current major player in the ecosystem: MyBinder. Among other results, we show how this growth in the production and delivery of notebooks made an important leap during the 2nd SARS-CoV-2 wave (July-September 2020). However, the general usage trend seems to have strongly decreased after the end of the most recent 7th wave (September 2022), coinciding with the official end of the global health crisis and all lockdown episodes. From these examined data, we conclude that COOLER and recent massive online learning scenarios have been very intimately linked. This fact may represent a flaw in the adoption of these exciting and useful learning materials.

Index Terms—Literate programming, notebooks, cloud, open educational resources, distant education, MyBinder.

I. LITERATE RESOURCES AND CLOUD SERVICES: A NEW LEARNING PARADIGM?

IN recent times, some open learning advocates began to openly publish and share their learning materials [47] as cohesively organized *live open educational resources* (OER). These types of assets usually comprise a single live document that contains the theoretical minimum, examples, runnable code sections, interactive questions/widgets, results, live graphics, and even comprehensive drawings and animations. All these elements are typically serialized, stored, and presented using Web standards (HTML5, JSON, JavaScript, etc.), and graphically organized as *chained cells* placed one after the other. These logical units act as *handholds*, guiding

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the student through the resolution of the scheduled exercise(s), i.e., they add *literacy* (or *narrative*) to the traditional *empty blank sheet*. Two examples of this type of open assets are shown in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2.

Fig. 1. Example of an LRP-based *notebook* with the usual contents and sections. This type of resource usually consists of cells that communicate with one another by exposing shared values/variables. The cells can either accommodate comments or allow the execution of code (or both). This example is hosted/run by Observable (<http://observablehq.com>).

The current biggest player in this literate resource paradigm (LRP) is the Jupyter project [40] and its associated *notebook* definition.

A Jupyter-based notebook can host literate and *non-reactive* code cells (i.e., they are not automatically re-run upon changes in other *client cells*) in almost any computer language (Python, JavaScript, Ruby, Golang, etc.) if the right kernel is correctly installed in the student's PC. Jupyter (together with Web-related regulations) has turned out one of the main players behind this bloom associated with *literate computational homework*.

The concept of LRP was originally coined by Donald Knuth [41] for the computer engineering realm but never took off or became a mainstream teaching paradigm. Nevertheless, the global confinement episodes caused by the planet-wide

Fig. 2. Another example of an Observable, LRP-based notebook with the usual contents and sections. This type of resource usually consists of cells that communicate with one another by exposing shared values/variables. The cells can either comment on something or allow the execution of code (or both). This example is hosted/run by Observable (tackled in Section III-D) and is available at https://bit.ly/bubble_19.

COVID-19 pandemic, seems to have boosted a notorious return of LRP to the education stage [25]. This trend can be also clearly appreciated in the Ngram plot on the term *literate programming* (Fig. 3). The Ngram Viewer is a tool provided by Google [46] that enables the analysis of the frequency of words or phrases in a large collection of books over a specified period. This figure shows how this computing/learning approach had an original upward trend when was first introduced by Knuth in the 80s and how it began to firmly reemerge around 2011.

Fig. 3. Normalized and Bezier-smoothed Ngram plots of the term *literate programming*, from 1985 to 2019.

Another push linked to the wide adoption of LRP has been the advent of cloud technologies. Despite the huge

advantages that the notebook-based approach brings to the learning ecosystem, some of the academic actors (both students and teachers) find the local deployment of the necessary technical environments (whether Jupyter-based or not) uneasy. This outlook worsens even further in online and/or informal settings, where the student is isolated and has no access to on-site assistance. As a result, a new trend has emerged that relies on the aforementioned cloud services for scaffolding and simplifying the notebook experience.

Cloud-served notebooks offer another important advantage for students: they allow collaboration by either editing the same document or forking from the original one. In the Jupyter domain, the main technology behind cloud-provided LRP documents is Binder [35]. In turn, MyBinder is a centralized (and free) Binder node that currently delivers around 14 million different notebooks with an average daily launch rate of 1.9k live documents (at least in the analyzed period). For these reasons, MyBinder is undoubtedly, the most successful actor in the *open cloud-provided literate space*.

These educational LRP-based items are managed and served by cloud companies. Hence, we coined the term *Cloud-Operated Open Literate Educational Resources*, or COOLER for short.

This new COOLER trend might represent an emerging learning paradigm and educational wave. However, truth be told, it is possible that this is a side effect caused by the global lockdown forced by the recent coronavirus epidemic. In the present work, we question ourselves this possibility by numerically and statistically analyzing its evolution over time, paying special attention to the influence caused by the recent SARS-CoV-2 global pandemic and the subsequent worldwide distant learning scenario. In more detail, we have examined (Section IV) the long-term logged activity (November 2018 - November 2023) reported by the MyBinder cloud service to answer the following research questions:

- How diverse is the nature of these educational resources?
- Is there a (measurable) relation between distant education and the use of COOLER?
- Is the recent COOLER wave intimately linked to the global lockdown caused by the Coronavirus?
- Are COOLER being actively leveraged after the end of the pandemic?

To address these questions, the rest of the paper has been organized as follows. In Section II, we briefly discuss previous research works around the fields related to cloud and OER. In Section III, we list the main players (institutions, projects, and technologies) behind the COOLER model. Next, Section IV describes the materials and methods used in our research. Finally, in Section V, we present and discuss the obtained results, and in Section VI some conclusions are drawn.

II. RELATED WORK

Although previous research works have identified and highlighted the advent and importance of cloud-based learning materials, very few studies have explored this tendency from a statistical point of view. The vast majority of the analyzed literature simply describes the different systems and methods.

Some claim they perform some sort of evaluation, but these analyses are usually carried out to measure the experience of a delimited group of students while using a specific system, praise advantages, qualitative discuss benefits or present current challenges. Next, we will review some of these works.

Authors in [12, 39, 62] qualitatively wonder whether MOOCs (*Massive Open Online Courses*) themselves could be treated as COOLERS. Other authors, such as [31, 48, 36, 2], present similar studies delimited in time and space (normally, in direct link with the COVID-19 pandemic).

Some reviews are field-characteristic. For instance:

- [11] explores the use of COOLER in the Microelectronics teaching realm.
- The authors in [38] do the same thing for Data Science.
- [7] presents a COOLER for geospatial education.
- [26] explores a cloud-based platform for education in the field of Dynamic Process Modeling.
- The ATLAS Collaboration at the European Organization for Nuclear Research (CERN) has introduced two genuine approaches ([75] and [22]) for the creation of cloud-based resources aimed at Particle Physics education.
- Authors in [19] introduce OSSCAR, aimed at Material Science cloud-based education.
- [43] presents an environment for Stellar Photometry in Astrophysics teaching on a cloud computing service.
- [28] introduces MLadder, an online training system for Machine Learning education.
- [53] implements a COOLER to foster professional engineering workforce skills.
- [58] has developed a cloud OER for teaching Database Systems.
- The potential of using Jupyter notebook in Physics education in high school students is studied by [63].
- [57] shows a COOLER for Computational Chemistry calculations.

Other studies emphasize the implementation of COOLER through specific proprietary environments:

- In [61], their authors suggested the use of Microsoft OneNote as a class notebook for the interactive and collaborative learning for remote teaching.
- [49] recommends the use of Wolfram Cloud as an interactive tool to support secondary school teaching.
- [27] proposes Deepnote notebooks for data science.
- [71] describes a custom designed mobile cloud computing platform to support synchronous learning.

Finally, some research works focus on the specific situation of COOLER in given geographical areas: Yemen [33], Philippines [72], China [76], etc.

However, most studies perform general/superficial reviews of cloud-based learning resources [77, 20, 4, 6, 18, 3, 1, 69, 1, 5, 56, 21, 68]. In other words, all these (and remarkable) research efforts, just contribute from a theoretical perspective and a speculative position. This is in contrast with our research, which is based on the long-term numerical and empirical analysis of raw usage data logged by the main and most global COOLER player at the moment: the Binder

project. This has allowed us to gain a more realistic insight about the exact situation and sincere health status of COOLER.

Fig. 4. Average percentage of papers related to the topic notebooks and education per country.

III. CLOUD SERVICES FOR LITERATE STEM TASKS

For the sake of completeness, we summarise here the current available COOLER alternatives. All of them share the same philosophy and goal: serving notebooks (based on a given technology or standard) from the cloud and for educational/research purposes. Some of them are Jupyter based, and some also rely on a superset service around it called JupyterHub (described in Section III-B). A few are even part of the Binder project (tackled next), and finally, some cloud notebook choices have nothing to do with the Jupyter technology set at all (Section III-D).

A. Members of the Binder Federation

The MyBinder site itself is a federation of BinderHub computing nodes and their corresponding mother institutions. BinderHub (written above JupyterHub) is the main technology underneath the Binder project. The main stakeholders of this alliance are:

The Binder team itself hosts the main node. It is in turn supported by Google (through the Google Kubernetes Engine [8]) and the Moore Foundation.

Gesis is the BinderHub node run by the Leibniz Institute for Social Sciences. This instance is targeted at studies related to social sciences and humanities research.

Turing Way is a node run by the Alan Turing Institute.

OVH is a France-based cloud-computing company that runs a BinderHub instance after a fruitful partnership agreement with the main Binder team.

In Table I, it is listed the average percentage of the requests managed by each of the members of the collaboration.

Any organization (academic institution, company, or research center) can deploy its BinderHub instance to accommodate its students, staff, scientists, etc. In turn, BinderHub depends on a Git-based hosting service (public or private). The most used services by the Binder project are listed in Table II. As it is possible to see, the current COOLER-sphere is very dependent on a single repo provider: GitHub.

¹<https://www.digital-science.com>

²<https://www.iq.harvard.edu>

TABLE I
MAIN MEMBERS OF THE BINDER FEDERATION.

Member	% requests	URL request origin
Binder team (Google Kubernetes Engine or GKE)	70.5	gke.mybinder.org
Gesis	18.7	gesis.mybinder.org notebooks.gesis.org
OVH	8.2	ovh.mybinder.org binder.mybinder.ovh
Turing	2.6	turing.mybinder.org binder.mybinder.turing.ac.uk

TABLE II
MAIN CODE (GIT) REPOSITORIES USED TO HOST JUPYTER-BASED NOTEBOOKS.

Provider	% use	Description
GitHub	99.156	Reputed cloud-based Git repository run by Microsoft Corporation.
Git	0.449	In-house Git-based servers.
GitLab [29]	0.377	Main technological opponent of GitHub, run by GitLab, Inc.
Zenodo [54]	0.010	Big data and digital library hosted by CERN. Available at https://zenodo.org .
Hydroshare [30]	0.004	Site managed by the Consortium of Universities for the Advancement of Hydrologic Science (CUAHSI) to share data models. Available at https://www.hydroshare.org .
Figshare [66]	0.003	Open access repository managed by the company Digital Science ¹ . Available at https://figshare.com .
Dataverse [15]	0.001	Open-source research data repository developed at the Harvard's Institute for Quantitative Social Science at Harvard ² (IQSS). Available at https://dataverse.harvard.edu .

B. JupyterHub- and BinderHub-based COOLER sites

The following notebook sites rely on BinderHub technology or JupyterHub. From a technical perspective, BinderHub is a Kubernetes-based service that allows the sharing of notebook environments from code repositories. The latter provides a scalable system for authenticating users and spawning single-user Jupyter servers. The most reputed ones are:

Pangeo is a computing community for big data in geosciences. Their Binder site is, of course, based on BinderHub, and although not part of the Binder Federation, it was the next to come online right after the MyBinder.org original node. Pangeo launched their public BinderHub instance in September 2018 [23]. They provide computational resources specialized in ocean, climate, satellite, and environmental research and education. The Pangeo cluster is hosted on the Google Kubernetes Engine and is available at <https://binder.pangeo.io>.

CERN SWAN or service for Web-based analysis is a Jupyter platform for interactive data analysis in the cloud [55, 50,

10]. It is available at <https://swan.web.cern.ch> and is run by CERN. SWAN is mainly aimed at guiding new CERN residents and students in the data mining techniques and tools usually operated by this international research institution.

PIMS or the Pacific Institute for Mathematical Sciences³ runs a service called Syzygy (available at <https://intro.syzygy.ca>). It deploys several JupyterHubs and BinderHubs for scientific/educational organizations in Canada. This entails that the user has to be registered in a Canadian research/education institution. For instance, the Syzygy node for McGill (Montreal) students can be accessed at <https://mcgill.syzygy.ca>.

SoS or scripts of scripts is a polyglot Jupyter notebook kernel and open workflow system for interactive multi-language data analysis and batch data processing. It is also available online and for free at <https://vatlab.github.io>. SoS has been developed by the MD Anderson Cancer Center⁴.

MyBinder itself is a BinderHub instance that provides all digital resources (the notebook engine, hosting, dependencies resolution, etc.) and exposes them through a public URL that can be remotely accessed. This URL will normally redirect the visitor to a running Jupyter notebook which has everything needed to fully run an LRP-based setting. In turn, MyBinder (and any BinderHub installation) relies on virtual containers (Docker being the main actor in this field). Containers are a very important component of the current COOLER, as it is demonstrated in the review work carried out in [42]. In fact, virtual containers were proposed as efficient reproducibility-enabled STEM environments already back in 2016 [14]. In many ways, together with Web standards, this virtualization technology is behind the momentum and level of adoption of the LRP+cloud tandem highlighted in the present work.

C. Jupyter notebook-based services

The following services rely on the Jupyter standard, but they have implemented their own in-house hosting methods and delivery technologies (i.e., they do not rely on BinderHub or any Binder-related technology). The most relevant ones are:

CoCalc allows the hosting of Jupyter and SageMath [78, 64] worksheets. It is available at <https://cocalc.com>.

Kaggle is an online community of data scientists and machine learning enthusiasts [24, 65]. Kaggle allows users to find and publish data sets, explore and build models in a Web-based data science environment, and work with other data scientists and machine-learning engineers. Kaggle also promotes competitions to solve data science challenges through its own Jupyter notebook environments. It is available at <https://www.kaggle.com/kernels>.

Colaboratory is part of the Google Research [9] team. Their goal is to allow any student to write and execute arbitrary Python code through the browser and, is especially well suited for data analysis and education. It is available at <https://colab.research.google.com>.

³<https://www.pims.math.ca>

⁴<https://www.mdanderson.org>

all the events are registered and made available to the public at <https://archive.analytics.mybinder.org>. This logging task is performed for the sake of transparency and research purposes and enables easy and flexible data-mining actions such as those carried out in this study. We analyse the following items and trends, as well:

- The daily, weekly, and monthly aggregated amount of managed and active repositories.
- The daily amount of launches.

Each JSONL file contains, among others, the following fields:

- Timestamp** is an ISO8601 formatted timestamp when the repository was launched, rounded down to the closest minute.
- Provider** is where the repository is hosted (GitHub, GitLab, or any other Git service).
- Spec** is a name identifying the repository.
- Ref** is a unique hash uniquely identifying the repository.
- Status** is a binary number stating whether the launch succeeded or failed.
- Origin** is which member of the Binder Federation ([Table I](#)) is serving the repository.

Additionally, an online open survey (<https://bit.ly/binderuse>) has been carried out among 350 MyBinder users to identify possible use cases, and their impact as a learning tool. Besides, to further and more objectively narrow our research to the educational realm, we have also looked for 150+ terms related to the Physics teaching domain in the aforementioned logs. Some of them appear as a word cloud plot in [Fig. 5](#).

Conjointly, we have overlaid data related to the evolution of the recent COVID-19 pandemic. In our case, we have used the information provided by the EU Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC) [16] and specifically, we have compiled the daily average number of cases (per European country). Finally, we have also compiled over 1000 literature references on the topics *notebooks*, *high school*, *higher education*, etc., in other to test the correlation (over the years and geographically) between COOLER usage and its real scientific impact.

All time-series plots have been smoothed for readability and to account for one-day outliers, weekdays/weekend differences, etc. In our case, all charts have been generated with GNUPlot 5.1 [34] and the Bezier splines option was used.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Following the open survey described in [Section IV](#) and as [Fig. 6](#) shows, half of the people that access any of the Binder Federation nodes do it for educational/learning purposes. This tells us that MyBinder is undoubtedly a COOLER central figure.

Certainly, most of the academic use of MyBinder is related to data science, machine learning, and other Python-centric technologies, as evinced by [Fig. 7](#). In fact science learning-related notebooks may represent less than a 5 %. According to the narrowed search performed by going through the terms appearing in [Fig. 5](#), the Physics-linked COOLER amount at

MyBinder just represents a humble 1.2 % (1.8×10^6 out of 14 million resources).

In [Fig. 8](#), it is shown the the number of monthly, weekly, and daily active repositories over the examined period. As it is evinced, a sudden growth took place during the 2nd SARS-CoV-2 wave (3-4 months after the global confinement started). However a steep drop seems to have taken place by the end of the health crisis (dark gray area). This plot also shows another moderated downturn by the end of the last winter semester (March-April 2023).

Fig. 6. Main areas and scenarios of usage of MyBinder. Almost half of the participants have acknowledged that they use MyBinder for educational purposes. Within this realm, again, half (51 %) of the participants use the COOLER paradigm in formal science learning settings (both pre- and university levels). The other half (49 %) use MyBinder for adult/upper/specialized training and informal education.

Fig. 7. Most used technologies by repositories served from MyBinder. Most of them are Python-related. They are also briefly described in [Table III](#).

Fig. 8. Unique active repositories since the start of MyBinder and over the period of a day, a week, and a month. The light gray area represents the 2nd SARS-CoV-2 wave and the darker one represents the timespan associated with the 7th wave and the agreed end of the global pandemic.

Fig. 7 and Fig. 9 reflect another big downside. This *variability vs. usage* cumulative histogram clearly shows that almost 80 % of the requested COOLERS correspond to just 40-45 specific repositories. This fact inevitably means that this genuine OER ecosystem runs the risk of being eventually cannibalised by only a few technologies, use cases, and/or learning layouts (mainly related to big data, analytics, machine learning, computer vision, data mining, etc.). In other words, if this progression persists, the education agents may think of COOLER as merely useful or appropriate for a certain and small range of applications (mainly related to the areas of Big Data and Artificial Intelligence).

TABLE III

MOST USED TECHNOLOGIES BY REPOSITORIES SERVED BY MEMBERS OF THE BINDER FEDERATION.

Technology	% use	Description
Python [51]	8	Reputed programming language that has become the <i>de facto</i> standard in the STEAM community.
Numpy [74]	19	Python library that adds support for large, multi-dimensional arrays and matrices.
Matplotlib [32]	27	Object-oriented Python plotting library.
Pandas [45]	23	Python library for data manipulation and analysis.
Seaborn	8	Python data visualization library.
Scipy [73]	15	Python library for scientific/technical research.

Fig. 9. Request/use percentage of the 5 to 100 most played COOLER items at MyBinder (presented as a cumulative histogram of requests vs. variety). As it can be seen, only just 40 repos represent more than 80 % of usage. This can be interpreted as a lack of variability in the type of applications, uses cases and technologies manageable by this STEAM notebook platform. It also may render Binder an excessively Python-centric and monolithic learning solution, which can, in turn, end up being categorized (by the teaching community) for tasks only related to these scenarios (big data, machine learning, etc.).

In Fig. 10, it is shown the daily evolution of the number of unique Physics-related repositories in contrast with the average progression in the number of COVID-19 cases in Europe. Again, sudden growth took place during the 2nd SARS-CoV-2 wave. However, this positive evolution seems to have also dissolved by the time the most adverse effects of the aforementioned health situation dissipated.

Besides, in Fig. 11, it is shown the total number of launched repos and Physics-related, per day. A steady increase can be seen. Nevertheless, a steep drop during the seventh (and less aggressive in health terms) COVID-19 wave can be

Fig. 10. Evolution in the number of Physics-related repos (per day) compared with the progression of the COVID-19 pandemic in Europe (average number of cases per day). The area highlighted in light gray corresponds to the 2nd SARS-CoV-2 wave and the darker one represents the timespan associated with the 7th wave and the agreed end of the global pandemic. COVID data was no longer officially compiled by the ECDC after October 2022.

appreciated for the general trend (starting with March 2022). It is interesting to note that, although the amount of Physics-related repositories is also decreasing, this decline is softer and even seems to be experimenting a recent steep increase (beginning of winter semester 2023).

In a tangential manner, in Fig. 14, it is shown the evolution of the expenses paid by the Binder project to run the MyBinder service. As it is possible to notice, there is a steep drop in these costs around the end of 2021 (reaching values close to 0 \$/€), which is in line with the progression also exhibited in Fig. 8, Fig. 10, and Fig. 11.

Fig. 11. Total number of repository launches (per day), both general and Physics-related (right and left axis, respectively). The area in gray represents the timespan associated with the 7th COVID-19 wave and the agreed end of the pandemic.

Finally, regarding the connection of COOLER usage and its scientific impact, Fig. 12 shows the evolution of literature papers on the topic *notebooks and education*. As it is possible to notice, a slight decrease is taking place in recent years. Likewise, Fig. 13 manifests a similar trend regarding the tuple *COOLER and high school education* (while the general tendency around *notebooks and research* still remains healthy in present times).

These two last results indicate that experts in the study of educational technologies are losing some interest in the COOLER paradigm (which is in correlation with the usage trends exhibited in Fig. 8, Fig. 10 and Fig. 11). Moreover, as

Fig. 4 also evinces, all scientific research around COOLER is being performed mainly in a handful of developed countries.

Fig. 12. Average percentage of papers (resampled monthly average) related to the topic notebooks and education (any level) per year and since the beginning of the research area.

Fig. 13. Average percentage of papers (monthly average) related to the topic notebooks and high school education (light-gray color) and notebooks and science (darker gray) per year and since the beginning of the research area.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we have analytically revised the status of the COOLER *universe* by analyzing the numbers provided by its current major player: Binder. This cloud-based LPR+OER approach has steadily made headway in recent years when it comes to carrying out online education-related tasks.

The recent COVID-19 pandemic and its associated home-confinement episodes have been responsible for the success of this paradigm. Many education centres began delegating their teaching methodologies to COOLER actors during the 2nd wave (summer of 2021). Nevertheless, the end of this global disease and the broad return to face-to-face education seems to have had a non-negligible negative impact on the Binder usage. The latest Binder data analyzed in this work also reflects another slightly unfavorable tendency in spring 2023. The evolution in the production of academic literature around the area shows a similar declining tendency.

There are also more downsides associated with this ecosystem. One of them is the proven excessive affinity to the Python language. Although it is a well-reputed technology, lots of other languages and frameworks, eventually risk being overlooked by the education community. A similar situation

is taking place in the Jupyter orbit itself, where the most used computing kernel is, again, Python. This implies that although Jupyter was designed to put aside its original Python-centric approach and grasp an open literate architecture, in practice, it still massively defaults to this programming language. Another tangible drawback is that the vast majority of these resources are devoted to Data Science and Artificial Intelligence and related topics. There is an undeniable lack of variability in MyBinder and hence, in the COOLER-space.

Anyway, given its easiness and openness, we cautiously suggest that these types of resources and their usage will grow in adoption in the long term, not only in online environments but also in ordinary classroom scenarios.

Fig. 14. Evolution of the costs (in \$) associated with the maintenance of the service. MyBinder publishes this information for the sake of transparency. The MyBinder project officially stopped logging costs after July 2022.

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